

Priorities of forming the methodology of institutional support of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy under conditions of instability

Relevance of the research topic. The modern scientific world is constantly changing and evolving. In this context, an important direction is the review of the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy.

Formulation of the problem. Innovation is a necessary condition for the formation of an effective national economy. However, existing models, methods and methodologies of entrepreneurship development in the scientific world are outdated. There is a need to review the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy.

Setting the goal and tasks of the research – to propose the basis of the formation of the methodology of the institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy.

Research method or methodology. The article uses the following methods: deduction and induction; abstraction; systematization and logical generalization.

Presentation of the main material (research results). Priorities for the formation of the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy are proposed. Its main orientations and implementation tools in the conditions of an unstable external environment are defined.

Field of application of results. The proposed foundations for the formation of the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy can be used by all interested market subjects who care about improving the functioning of entrepreneurship and innovation.

Conclusions according to the article. The scientific schools within which it is expedient to form the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy have been determined. The author's vision of a set of tools for determining priorities for the formation of the methodology of institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy is proposed.

Keywords: institutional support, innovation, economy, entrepreneurship.

Пріоритети формування методології інституціонального забезпечення підприємництва в інноваційній економіці за умов нестабільності

Актуальність теми дослідження. Сучасний науковий світ постійно змінюється та еволюціонує. У такому контексті важливим напрямком є перегляд методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці.

Постановка проблеми. Інновації є необхідною умовою формування ефективної національної економіки. Однак існуючи у науковому світі моделі, методи та методології розвитку підприємництва є застарілими. Існує потреба перегляду методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – запропонувати основи формування методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано методи: дедукції та індукції; абстрагування; систематизації й логічного узагальнення.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Запропоновано пріоритети формування методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці. Визначено її головні орієнтири та інструменти впровадження в умовах нестабільного зовнішнього середовища.

Галузь застосування результатів. Запропоновані основи формування методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці можуть використовуватися усіма зацікавленим суб'єктам ринку, які піклуються про покращення функціонування підприємництва та інновацій.

Висновки за статтею. Визначено наукові школи в межах яких доцільно формувати методологію інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці. Запропоновано авторське бачення набору інструментів для визначення пріоритетів формування методології інституціонального розвитку підприємництва в інноваційній економіці.

Ключові слова: інституціональне забезпечення, інновації, економіка, підприємство.

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The modern world is developing in conditions of globalization. Not always existing directions and proposals for improving the work of entrepreneurship are relevant. There is a need to review the methods of modern business development taking into account current trends.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, which initiated the solution of this problem and on which the author relies, highlighting previously unsolved parts of the general problem, which is the subject of this article. Many authors have researched methods of business development [1–4]. Tools and methods of improving its work were considered in scientific works [5–8]. However, the world is constantly changing. Therefore, it is necessary to update scientific views.

Formulation of the goals of the article (setting the task) – to propose the basis of the formation of the methodology of the institutional development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results. In many cases, when studying the economic situation of an enterprise, the performance indicator is influenced by not one, but several factors. References to scientific studies of neo-institutionalism actualize the importance of improving institutional support with the aim of the most effective development of the innovative economy. The representatives of the specified scientific school emphasize that the innovative development achieved by the country is the merit of the actions of institutions that create conditions, stimulate, limit, regulate and prohibit fraudulent actions in society, which in turn motivates the competitive

behavior of market subjects and forces them to improve the quality of their production or service provision. A significant number of studies and observations of the work of the institutes proved that, having a significant role in supporting the social and economic security of society, they had a fundamentally different evolutionary path of their development according to the countries of the world. In our view, the consequences of these differences are as follows: the inheritance of Soviet tools of state regulation, which shaped the Soviet way of development of institutions rigidly subordinated vertically; the diversity of resource provision of the territories where the institutes were developed, which affected their further development path; presence of corruption, bureaucracy, weak legislative field, low socio-economic development of society and passive participation of citizens in the life of institutions; the priority or vice versa of the innovative path of development and scientific research, which determined the model of the formation of the institutional matrix. In general, the mentality, political situation, market conditions, prevailing types of ownership, models of state regulation, legal norms, ideological beliefs and customs laid the evolutionary path for the development of markets and institutions. Despite the fact that these differences help to explain more deeply the reasons for different conditions of functioning of institutions, the role of the state and society in encouraging qualitative transformations of institutions in the short- and medium-term perspective should also be taken into account. In this context, the importance of the quality of institutions and, accordingly, institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy becomes important. Because, it is important to understand that any methodology is not static, and therefore

the «institutional quality» is on the agenda, which must be ensured by the new methodology, taking into account the fact that the institution and economic development are mutually determining, and the change in the political situation violates the institutional balance and work of institutions, forcing them to constantly adjust and adapt. And it is precisely the tools that will help institutes to adapt and perform their functions in the best way that the updated methodology, methodology and new scientific thought in general should reveal. Complex modernization of the national economy assumes that institutions should grow in parallel with the level of socio-economic development.

It is a logical cause-and-effect relationship that the acceleration of scientific and technological progress and technological production stimulates the improvement of the quality of life and is the basis for the functioning of effective institutions in the institutional environment. Such institutes should be transparent, fair to all market participants and have mutually beneficial communication links with science and business. On the other hand, interested market stakeholders should create institutional dynamics by initiating institutional changes and improving the work of institutions. Therefore, stable socio-economic development, high quality of life of the population leads to active institutional transformations, which are dictated by the current conditions of the development of society. It is clear that other intangible factors such as strong human capital, digitalization and open markets are also driving institutional change and forcing a review of existing institutional arrangements. Moreover, most authors determine that the quality of institutional support should be high in all institutions at the same time. As an example, the authors, without even dividing the institutions, emphasize the totality of the functioning of an effective institution as a mandatory component of the innovative economy. In our view, such indirect consideration of the institute with the absence of their detailing is a shortcoming of modern scientific thought. Because each evolutionary period of society's development is dictated by the dominance of a certain paradigm of development, with its own accents and impulses stimulating development. According to D. North, the institute is not the only active structure, but the opposite. The rules of the game, customs and norms create entire systems of institutions, par-

ticipate in the social, economic, and political life of society. The above rightly focuses our attention on the existence of various institutions that function in different ways, interact with each other, and most importantly, have different levels of resistance to the necessary changes. For example, in countries with excessive political influence on society (North Korea, China, India), political institutions are of the greatest importance for the formation of institutional support. In more democratic countries, social, economic and educational institutions set the trend of social development and influence the behavior model of key market actors. This segmentation determines the need to take into account the type of political system as a mandatory approach to the development of the methodology of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy and taking into account the circumstances that encourage qualitative positive changes.

This is a certain taxonomy for the study of a complex system of institutional support, where the prioritization of an individual institution can stimulate positive consequences for the entire institutional matrix, or at least have leverage to maintain its stability and balance in response to turbulence in global and regional dimensions. The «plasticity» of institutions to changes and unforeseen circumstances, in such a case, will be determined by a successfully developed modern methodology, which will provide for a set of tasks, functions, principles and measures to reduce opportunistic resistance, increase the levers of influence of leading institutions on others, which will trigger positive shifts in general.

Political institutions are a relatively little-studied concept in modern neo-institutional science. Their definition is rather vague and contradictory, as are the functions that scientists assign to them. A. D. Pakharev, in our opinion, provides a fairly thorough definition and classification of them: «... political institutions as institutions capable of making political decisions and translating them into relevant legal norms and practices of state-political and civil life. The totality of such institutions that exercise power and manage society constitutes the political system of a particular state...the structure of state political institutions includes: the state itself, its power structures, legislative bodies of power in the center and localities, central and local bodies of executive power, higher and local judicial bodies,

bodies of prosecutorial supervision, mass media, or, as they are often called, the «fourth power» [9, с. 7–8]. Economic institutions form prescriptions, prohibitions or permits in the economic environment, respectively social and educational in the field of social protection of the population, social policy or science, technology and education. However, each of the institutions differs in the level of «plasticity» and the ability to change, taking into account the political environment inherent in a certain society. In countries with high pressure of power on society and control over institutional changes, political institutions have a significant impact on the economy, thereby changing economic dynamics and redistribution of resources. The retrospect of institutional development shows that the unfair influence of political institutions on others unbalances the institutional environment and does not contribute to the development of innovation and business. At the same time, balanced and targeted influence, on the contrary, stimulates production, knowledge and innovative activity. The diversity of institutions emphasizes their individual importance and relevance for innovative economy and entrepreneurship, but at the same time demonstrates their dependence on each other. Under the conditions of the country's choice of a course for the development of entrepreneurship and innovative economy, no institute should dominate another or take over its functions there and then curtailing the activities of the rest. In this sense, it is necessary to separately examine the influence of each institution on the innovative economy and entrepreneurship and avoid monopolizing one of them. This is quite a difficult task, because usually, political institutions are dominant and generally represent the political construction of the ruling elite.

Conclusions

The development of science is not static. There is a need for constant revision of the main methods, tools and methodologies for the development of innovative entrepreneurship. Given the instability of the institutional environment, such review should be timely and continuous.

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